

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: NKRUMAH****FIRST NAME: BERNARD****PROGRAM CODE: PHGH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on IOS)

EFFECTIVE ACADEMIC WRITING: GETTING THE BASICS RIGHT

1) INTRODUCTION

This course, in my view, has been designed by Euclid University to ensure that as a doctorate level student I am adequately oriented and prepared for high level graduate writing by providing me with basic and essential materials and skills. Haven been involved in a number of academic and health research activities, and also recently completing a masters level program, I was of the view I had adequate knowledge and skill to write effectively. However, this toolkit has proved to be extra beneficial. I am particularly trilled about the depth and details of the toolkit which clearly indicates to me the seriousness I am expected to attach to this program as well as the granularity and precision with which to write. As a public health specialist and now a student of global health and health systems, the delivery of accurate and quality information in a timely manner could be the difference between life and death, I am thus very appreciative of the guidance provided in these materials.

2) COURSE PACK FOR PERIOD 1

The material provided for the first period of the “International Academic Writing” course is an eighty-three-page long material that is divided into various sections. The first section of the course pack deals with the basics of essay writing. This section details out a seven-point steps that students must follow and practise to help then to write good essays (EUCLID 2015, 2-5). I like the way this section has been simplified and outlined. I do

appreciate a couple of points from this section, namely: 1) starting work early, 2) organizing my ideas, and 3) editing the essay. I have not really taken time to consider how important these points are and the impact it has on writing when well considered and practiced. I would typically form my writing ideas in my mind and once am clear with what I wish to write, I zoom into it. I have also been caught pants down a couple of times due to late writing. The problem with this as I experienced is the lack of adequate time to thoroughly review the work before the submission deadline. It is my goal to always start assignments early and by extension submit early as well.

The second part of the course pack is what appears to be a power point presentation which also touches on some very critical issues on paper writing. Plagiarism is indeed a serious offense in academic and scientific writing and I do appreciate the literature provided in the course pack. About a year ago, I was introduced to the term ‘self-plagiarism’ when I submitted a work in which I used portions of my own previous work without adequately acknowledging ‘myself.’ This came as a shock to me! Until then, I never knew there was anything like ‘self-plagiarism.’ The authors of this section demonstrated how Euclid University takes plagiarism seriously. I particularly liked the literature on citing, being it, in-text citing or list of works cited. I have been using Endnote reference manager and American Psychological Association (APA) style of citing for a while, however, the opportunity to now learn and use Zotero reference manager with the Turabian style is an interesting and welcomed opportunity. The use of quotations, paraphrases and formatting in writing were areas in this literature that I had not really paid attention to in the past as I thought were normal to me as a native English speaker but going through this course work, there were more details and clarity that I had no idea of. For example; the use of double and single quotation marks.

The section on “Some Rules of Thumb for Writing Papers” was a great chance for me to refresh my memory on the key essentials needed for effective writing (EUCLID 2015, 43–45). The authors of this material listed ten key points that need consideration by students. Two of the points were of interest to me:

1) Clarity in writing. This has been stressed a couple of times in earlier pages of this course pack but what keeps playing in my mind is where certain technical terms or procedures need to be written and or explained using such technical terminologies. Would this be considered as lack of clarity to a third person who may not be familiar within the field of the discussion or write up?

2) I asked myself a couple of times if anyone at this level would not take his/her writing seriously, however sections of this literature such as “try to get “inside” the conception you are discussing; develop a sense of its internal integrity, and see if you are able to understand how someone (who may have strange ideas, but is neither moron nor sociopath) might have come to hold the views in question” threw more light on this notion (EUCLID 2015, 44). In effect, I must learn to put myself in the shoes of the person or group of persons the writing is aimed at by asking questions they are likely to ask and attempt to the address those questions in my writing.

I did appreciate the eleven important reminders listed in the “Lit – 101 Review” section of the course pack as well as “essential questions and answers” (EUCLID 2015, 46–51). Questions 9 and 16 got my attention. Most often I tend to write out numbers in letters and then put the numerals in parenthesis. The guidance provided however is quite helpful, as my understanding is to keep numbers written in numerals but in letters if it starts a sentence. I do agree with the authors that keeping to a consistent format when using numbers is very important. I do not recall having challenges with the use of “I” and “me.” I think their use is quite clear and well defined either as a “subject” or an “object” pronoun (EUCLID 2015, 50).

3) TWO STYLES OF WRITING: APA AND TURABIAN

Euclid University requires students to use two different writing styles throughout the study program. These are the Chicago Manual of Style, also known as the Turabian Style and the APA style (EUCLID 2015, 66). Even though the Chicago and Turabian styles are the same, the Chicago style is mostly preferred for formatting books and research papers and the Turabian’s style for research papers, theses, and dissertations. For the EUCLID program, the Turabian style is recommended for major papers whilst the APA is recommended for response papers.

I have used the APA style of writing severally so I can say I have some level of familiarity with its use. I recently completed a master program for which the whole course work (group discussions, short and long essays as well as project work) were all done in the APA Style.

The Turabian style is however new to me. I have never used it before and so this experience is not only new but also challenging with respect to switching from one familiar style to an unknown style. I feel confident that with time I will be able to master the art of using the Turabian style as well.

It is also worth to note the other materials and literature on “Latin Abbreviations and expressions” the “Common Latin Abbreviations Used in Writing” and the “Commonly Used Latin Expressions” (EUCLID 2015, 78 & 81). These have been a good refresher and a reference tools for this program.

4) CONCLUSION

After completing a master level program recently, I believed I had sufficient skill and knowledge in academic writing. I must admit this course material has open a new level of details and accuracy in academic writing for different audience and settings. Being a public health practitioner, preparing and using questionnaires and assessments tools either during disease outbreaks situations or for routine surveillance is a regular activity that requires a great deal of attention, deals and accuracy. Learning to use the two writing styles at Euclid University though poses a challenge will further improve my work eventually.

A review of the course material in terms of writing style, grammar, citing, etc has been quite interesting. It has got me rethinking about my writing abilities as well as introduced me to useful materials to help me improve. I, however, wish the materials are page numbered to make referencing much easier as sometimes manually counting the pages gets confusing.

REFERENCE

EUCLID. 2015. *ACA-401D Coursepack*. Accessed on October 22, 2019 <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1/>.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.